

An Interactive Decision Tree-Based Evolutionary Multi-Objective Algorithm: Supplementary Material

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This supplementary material provides details of experimental design and results of the main paper that had been omitted for brevity.

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I. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN & RESULTS

Table I: Specifications of the tests. **P** indicates the benchmark problem. Type corresponds to the DM types shown in Table 1 of the main paper (for minimization). n : dimension of the problem. m : dimension of the objective space. $U(\mathbf{z}^{\text{MPS}})$: utility of $\mathbf{z}^{\text{MPS}}$. $U(\mathbf{z}^w)$: utility of the worst PF solution. UF column specifies the utility function used in the test where “tst” stands for the Stewart UF and “tch” for the Tchebychef UF.

Test	P	n	m	Type	$U(\mathbf{z}^{\text{MPS}})$	$U(\mathbf{z}^w)$	UF
1	1	6	2	1	0.1023	0.8976	tst
2	1	6	2	2	0.0101	0.9038	tst
3	1	6	2	3	0.3128	0.9970	tst
4	1	6	2	4	0.1426	0.9378	tst
5	1	6	2	-	0.1159	0.3476	tch
6	1	14	10	1	0.0002	0.2164	tst
7	1	14	10	2	0.0001	0.1609	tst
8	1	14	10	3	0.0215	0.8690	tst
9	1	14	10	4	0.0108	0.7716	tst
10	1	14	10	-	0.0397	0.2404	tch
11	2	11	2	1	0.3660	0.6364	tst
12	2	11	2	2	0.1062	0.8933	tst
13	2	11	2	3	0.4627	0.9996	tst
14	2	11	2	4	0.1261	0.9977	tst
15	2	11	2	-	0.3170	0.7653	tch
16	2	19	10	1	0.0003	0.2953	tst
17	2	19	10	2	0.0001	0.2448	tst
18	2	19	10	3	0.1117	0.9695	tst
19	2	19	10	4	0.0217	0.8263	tst
20	2	19	10	-	0.0675	0.2446	tch
21	7	21	2	1	0.1259	0.9692	tst
22	7	21	2	2	0.1097	0.8894	tst
23	7	21	2	3	0.4061	1.0000	tst
24	7	21	2	4	0.3525	0.9999	tst
25	7	21	2	-	0.0402	0.8506	tch
26	7	29	10	1	0.0016	0.8045	tst
27	7	29	10	2	0.0007	0.7638	tst
28	7	29	10	3	0.1238	0.9927	tst
29	7	29	10	4	0.0460	0.9842	tst
30	7	29	10	-	0.0580	0.2113	tch
31	1	8	4	1	0.3560	0.8928	tst
32	1	8	4	2	0.0047	0.3643	tst
33	1	8	4	3	0.3019	0.8759	tst
34	1	8	4	4	0.0047	0.3781	tst
35	1	8	4	-	0.0405	0.1589	tch
36	2	13	4	1	0.3267	0.9936	tst
37	2	13	4	2	0.0253	0.5428	tst
38	2	13	4	3	0.4150	0.9989	tst
39	2	13	4	4	0.0214	0.5193	tst
40	2	13	4	-	0.0567	0.3222	tch
41	7	23	4	1	0.1481	0.9993	tst
42	7	23	4	2	0.0111	0.6991	tst
43	7	23	4	3	0.3269	0.9992	tst
44	7	23	4	4	0.0228	0.7759	tst
45	7	23	4	-	0.0699	0.4371	tch

Table II: The parameters and the ranges that are used in cross validation of DTEMOA

Splitter	best, random
max_depth	$m - 100$
min_samples_leaf	1-3

Table III: The results of experiments under ideal conditions for BCEMOA, DTEMOA and iTDEA. The mean (and standard deviation in parenthesis) over 20 independent runs is shown for each test. The values are rounded to 2 decimal points. The performance of DTEMOA is compared with iTDEA and BCEMOA and the better values are indicated with letter 'i' or 'b' (indicating iTDEA or BCEMOA) to highlight the winner where $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ for Wilcoxon test. P : ID of the DTLZ benchmark problem. m : dimension of the objective space. type: DM type.

Test	P	m	type	BCEMOA			DTEMOA			iTDEA		
				2	3	4	2	3	4	2	3	4
Stewart UF												
1	1	2	1	0.19(0.2)	0.19(0.2)	0.19(0.2)	0.18(0.22)b	0.18(0.22)b	0.18(0.22)b	0.1(0.0)i	0.1(0.0)i	0.12(0.02)i
2	1	2	2	0.16(0.32)	0.16(0.33)	0.15(0.33)	0.12(0.27)	0.12(0.27)	0.12(0.27)b	0.01(0.0)	0.01(0.0)i	0.02(0.01)i
3	1	2	3	0.61(0.27)	0.57(0.27)	0.57(0.27)	0.6(0.23)	0.59(0.24)	0.59(0.24)	0.37(0.06)i	0.5(0.19)	0.5(0.19)
4	1	2	4	0.34(0.34)	0.34(0.34)	0.34(0.34)	0.28(0.3)	0.28(0.3)	0.28(0.3)i	0.14(0.0)i	0.14(0.0)i	0.32(0.32)
6	1	10	1	0.07(0.07)	0.07(0.07)	0.06(0.07)	0.03(0.05)b	0.02(0.05)b	0.02(0.05)b	0.01(0.01)	0.01(0.01)	0.01(0.01)
7	1	10	2	0.05(0.06)	0.05(0.06)	0.05(0.06)	0.01(0.04)b	0.01(0.03)b	0.01(0.03)b	0.0(0.01)	0.0(0.01)	0.0(0.01)
8	1	10	3	0.16(0.13)	0.15(0.14)	0.15(0.14)	0.14(0.11)	0.13(0.12)	0.12(0.11)i	0.17(0.09)	0.17(0.09)	0.17(0.09)
9	1	10	4	0.15(0.09)	0.14(0.08)	0.14(0.08)	0.13(0.11)	0.11(0.12)b	0.1(0.11)b	0.15(0.1)	0.15(0.1)	0.15(0.1)
11	2	2	1	0.37(0.01)	0.37(0.01)	0.37(0.01)	0.37(0.0)i	0.37(0.02)	0.37(0.01)i	0.37(0.0)	0.37(0.0)i	0.37(0.0)
12	2	2	2	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)i	0.11(0.0)i	0.11(0.0)i	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)
13	2	2	3	0.47(0.03)b	0.47(0.03)b	0.47(0.03)b	0.49(0.03)	0.49(0.03)i	0.49(0.03)i	0.47(0.01)	0.5(0.04)	0.5(0.04)
14	2	2	4	0.21(0.23)	0.2(0.23)	0.2(0.23)b	0.22(0.24)	0.22(0.24)	0.22(0.24)i	0.13(0.0)	0.13(0.0)	0.46(0.38)
16	2	10	1	0.02(0.02)	0.02(0.01)	0.02(0.01)	0.01(0.01)b	0.0(0.01)b	0.0(0.01)b	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)
17	2	10	2	0.01(0.01)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)
18	2	10	3	0.25(0.1)	0.25(0.1)	0.23(0.09)	0.18(0.05)bi	0.18(0.06)bi	0.17(0.05)bi	0.39(0.12)	0.39(0.12)	0.39(0.12)
19	2	10	4	0.14(0.07)	0.14(0.07)	0.13(0.06)	0.12(0.06)	0.1(0.06)bi	0.1(0.06)bi	0.15(0.08)	0.15(0.08)	0.15(0.08)
21	7	2	1	0.2(0.23)	0.2(0.23)	0.2(0.23)	0.24(0.27)	0.24(0.27)	0.24(0.27)	0.13(0.01)	0.39(0.37)	0.39(0.37)
22	7	2	2	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)bi	0.11(0.0)bi	0.11(0.0)bi	0.11(0.01)	0.11(0.01)	0.14(0.15)
23	7	2	3	0.43(0.07)b	0.43(0.07)b	0.43(0.07)b	0.45(0.08)	0.45(0.08)	0.45(0.08)	0.44(0.07)	0.48(0.09)	0.48(0.09)
24	7	2	4	0.38(0.09)b	0.38(0.09)b	0.38(0.09)b	0.41(0.11)	0.4(0.11)	0.4(0.11)	0.38(0.05)	0.46(0.14)	0.46(0.14)
26	7	10	1	0.09(0.09)	0.1(0.11)	0.22(0.0)	0.04(0.04)bi	0.04(0.04)	0.04(0.04)	0.05(0.07)	0.01(0.01)	0.0(0.0)
27	7	10	2	0.08(0.09)	0.12(0.1)	0.01(0.0)	0.02(0.02)bi	0.02(0.02)b	0.02(0.02)	0.02(0.05)	0.03(0.06)	0.0(0.0)
28	7	10	3	0.36(0.16)	0.15(0.08)	0.12(0.0)	0.23(0.12)b	0.19(0.12)	0.17(0.11)	0.17(0.15)i	0.17(0.13)	0.26(0.0)
29	7	10	4	0.23(0.15)	0.13(0.08)	0.17(0.0)	0.14(0.15)b	0.1(0.13)	0.09(0.13)	0.12(0.16)i	0.1(0.1)	0.2(0.0)
31	1	4	1	0.49(0.12)	0.48(0.13)	0.47(0.13)	0.48(0.12)i	0.47(0.12)i	0.47(0.12)i	0.59(0.09)	0.59(0.09)	0.59(0.09)
32	1	4	2	0.05(0.09)	0.05(0.09)	0.05(0.11)	0.05(0.1)i	0.05(0.1)i	0.05(0.1)i	0.12(0.12)	0.12(0.12)	0.12(0.12)
33	1	4	3	0.45(0.11)	0.46(0.12)	0.43(0.11)	0.43(0.11)bi	0.43(0.11)i	0.43(0.11)i	0.56(0.11)	0.56(0.11)	0.56(0.11)
34	1	4	4	0.05(0.09)	0.04(0.09)	0.04(0.09)	0.03(0.06)i	0.03(0.06)i	0.03(0.06)i	0.1(0.13)	0.1(0.13)	0.1(0.13)
36	2	4	1	0.52(0.15)	0.49(0.17)	0.47(0.16)	0.43(0.14)bi	0.43(0.14)i	0.42(0.14)i	0.85(0.14)	0.85(0.14)	0.85(0.14)
37	2	4	2	0.05(0.03)	0.05(0.03)	0.05(0.03)	0.04(0.03)bi	0.04(0.01)bi	0.04(0.01)bi	0.13(0.09)	0.13(0.09)	0.13(0.09)
38	2	4	3	0.55(0.12)	0.54(0.12)	0.53(0.11)	0.52(0.11)i	0.5(0.1)i	0.51(0.1)i	0.88(0.12)	0.88(0.12)	0.88(0.12)
39	2	4	4	0.03(0.01)	0.03(0.01)	0.03(0.02)	0.03(0.02)bi	0.03(0.02)i	0.03(0.02)bi	0.11(0.09)	0.11(0.09)	0.11(0.09)
41	7	4	1	0.28(0.16)	0.26(0.14)	0.25(0.13)	0.18(0.08)bi	0.17(0.08)bi	0.17(0.07)i	0.29(0.19)	0.37(0.22)	0.43(0.26)
42	7	4	2	0.03(0.02)	0.03(0.02)	0.03(0.02)	0.02(0.01)bi	0.02(0.01)i	0.02(0.0)i	0.05(0.05)	0.06(0.07)	0.06(0.08)
43	7	4	3	0.45(0.15)	0.44(0.14)	0.44(0.15)	0.42(0.13)	0.42(0.13)i	0.42(0.12)i	0.44(0.13)	0.5(0.15)	0.54(0.17)
44	7	4	4	0.12(0.06)	0.11(0.05)	0.1(0.05)	0.11(0.05)i	0.08(0.05)bi	0.07(0.04)bi	0.16(0.06)	0.15(0.08)	0.17(0.07)
Tchebychef UF												
5	1	2	-	0.14(0.05)	0.14(0.05)	0.14(0.05)	0.13(0.04)	0.13(0.04)	0.13(0.04)i	0.12(0.01)i	0.12(0.01)i	0.14(0.03)
10	1	10	-	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.05(0.02)i	0.05(0.02)i	0.05(0.02)bi	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)
15	2	2	-	0.32(0.0)	0.32(0.0)	0.32(0.0)	0.32(0.0)i	0.32(0.0)i	0.32(0.0)i	0.33(0.01)	0.33(0.01)	0.37(0.05)
20	2	10	-	0.08(0.01)	0.08(0.01)	0.08(0.01)	0.07(0.01)bi	0.07(0.01)bi	0.07(0.01)bi	0.11(0.03)	0.11(0.03)	0.11(0.03)
25	7	2	-	0.04(0.0)	0.05(0.05)	0.04(0.01)	0.04(0.0)i	0.04(0.0)i	0.04(0.0)i	0.1(0.1)	0.04(0.0)	0.04(0.0)
30	7	10	-	0.12(0.01)	0.12(0.02)	0.12(0.0)	0.1(0.01)b	0.1(0.01)b	0.1(0.01)b	0.06(0.03)i	0.06(0.02)i	0.05(0.02)i
35	1	4	-	0.06(0.02)	0.06(0.02)	0.05(0.02)	0.05(0.02)bi	0.05(0.02)i	0.05(0.02)i	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)
40	2	4	-	0.08(0.04)	0.08(0.03)	0.08(0.03)	0.07(0.02)i	0.07(0.02)i	0.07(0.02)i	0.17(0.06)	0.17(0.06)	0.17(0.06)
45	7	4	-	0.1(0.04)	0.1(0.04)	0.1(0.04)	0.09(0.02)i	0.08(0.02)i	0.08(0.01)i	0.11(0.06)	0.13(0.08)	0.15(0.08)

Table IV: The results of experiments with simulation of inconsistencies in DM’s decisions for BCEMOA, DTEMOA and iTDEA. The mean (and standard deviation in parenthesis) over 20 independent runs is shown for each test. The values are rounded to 2 decimal points. The performance of DTEMOA is compared with iTDEA and BCEMOA and the better values are indicated with letter ‘i’ or ‘b’ (indicating iTDEA or BCEMOA) to highlight the winner where $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ for Wilcoxon test. P : ID of the DTLZ benchmark problem. m : dimension of the objective space. type: DM type.

Test	P	m	type	BCEMOA				DTEMOA				iTDEA			
				$\sigma = 0.005$	$\sigma = 0.01$	$\sigma = 0.1$	$\sigma = 0.2$	$\sigma = 0.005$	$\sigma = 0.01$	$\sigma = 0.1$	$\sigma = 0.2$	$\sigma = 0.005$	$\sigma = 0.01$	$\sigma = 0.1$	$\sigma = 0.2$
Stewart UF															
1	1	2	1	0.25(0.32)	0.25(0.32)	0.26(0.32)	0.28(0.32)	0.2(0.25)b	0.19(0.23)b	0.17(0.2)b	0.16(0.16)b	0.1(0.0)i	0.1(0.0)i	0.12(0.02)i	0.15(0.07)i
2	1	2	2	0.13(0.28)	0.13(0.28)	0.14(0.29)	0.22(0.35)	0.1(0.24)	0.1(0.24)	0.08(0.2)	0.07(0.17)b	0.01(0.0)i	0.01(0.0)i	0.03(0.04)	0.04(0.05)
3	1	2	3	0.54(0.28)	0.57(0.27)	0.62(0.26)	0.66(0.26)	0.62(0.22)	0.62(0.22)	0.6(0.23)	0.58(0.24)	0.49(0.19)	0.49(0.19)	0.49(0.2)	0.51(0.21)
4	1	2	4	0.35(0.36)	0.35(0.36)	0.36(0.36)	0.37(0.36)	0.28(0.3)b	0.28(0.3)b	0.28(0.29)b	0.28(0.3)b	0.14(0.0)i	0.15(0.0)i	0.16(0.02)i	0.16(0.03)i
6	1	10	1	0.09(0.08)	0.07(0.07)	0.1(0.1)	0.12(0.1)	0.03(0.06)b	0.02(0.05)b	0.03(0.06)b	0.03(0.06)b	0.01(0.01)	0.01(0.01)	0.01(0.01)	0.01(0.01)
7	1	10	2	0.05(0.06)	0.04(0.06)	0.08(0.07)	0.1(0.09)	0.01(0.04)b	0.01(0.04)b	0.02(0.05)b	0.01(0.03)b	0.0(0.01)	0.0(0.01)	0.0(0.01)	0.0(0.01)
8	1	10	3	0.14(0.09)	0.14(0.09)	0.2(0.15)	0.27(0.18)	0.14(0.12)	0.14(0.12)	0.13(0.1)bi	0.13(0.09)bi	0.17(0.09)	0.17(0.09)	0.17(0.09)	0.17(0.09)
9	1	10	4	0.14(0.09)	0.15(0.09)	0.18(0.12)	0.21(0.13)	0.12(0.1)	0.11(0.1)	0.12(0.1)b	0.11(0.11)b	0.15(0.1)	0.15(0.1)	0.15(0.1)	0.15(0.1)
11	2	2	1	0.37(0.0)	0.37(0.02)	0.42(0.08)	0.44(0.1)	0.37(0.0)bi	0.37(0.0)b	0.37(0.01)bi	0.37(0.01)bi	0.37(0.0)	0.37(0.0)i	0.4(0.04)	0.45(0.09)
12	2	2	2	0.11(0.02)	0.12(0.03)	0.16(0.14)	0.14(0.03)	0.11(0.0)bi	0.11(0.0)bi	0.11(0.01)bi	0.11(0.01)bi	0.11(0.0)	0.11(0.0)	0.13(0.03)	0.14(0.03)
13	2	2	3	0.49(0.05)	0.49(0.05)	0.55(0.16)	0.56(0.16)	0.48(0.03)i	0.48(0.03)i	0.48(0.03)i	0.49(0.04)bi	0.5(0.04)	0.5(0.04)	0.53(0.08)	0.63(0.21)
14	2	2	4	0.25(0.27)	0.29(0.31)	0.27(0.3)	0.27(0.28)	0.21(0.23)	0.21(0.23)b	0.19(0.2)b	0.16(0.15)bi	0.13(0.0)i	0.13(0.0)i	0.17(0.17)i	0.26(0.3)
16	2	10	1	0.02(0.01)	0.03(0.03)	0.05(0.04)	0.05(0.05)	0.01(0.01)b	0.01(0.01)b	0.01(0.02)b	0.01(0.01)b	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)
17	2	10	2	0.01(0.0)	0.01(0.01)	0.02(0.04)	0.02(0.03)	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.01)b	0.0(0.0)b	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)	0.0(0.0)
18	2	10	3	0.27(0.09)	0.26(0.07)	0.32(0.16)	0.35(0.17)	0.17(0.03)bi	0.17(0.05)bi	0.19(0.07)bi	0.21(0.11)bi	0.39(0.12)	0.39(0.12)	0.39(0.12)	0.39(0.12)
19	2	10	4	0.14(0.07)	0.13(0.06)	0.15(0.07)	0.18(0.11)	0.09(0.06)bi	0.1(0.06)bi	0.1(0.06)bi	0.13(0.09)b	0.15(0.08)	0.15(0.08)	0.15(0.08)	0.15(0.08)
21	7	2	1	0.2(0.23)	0.2(0.23)	0.21(0.23)	0.21(0.23)	0.22(0.25)	0.2(0.23)b	0.16(0.16)bi	0.16(0.16)bi	0.32(0.33)	0.32(0.33)	0.32(0.33)	0.28(0.31)
22	7	2	2	0.11(0.0)	0.15(0.17)	0.19(0.23)	0.19(0.23)	0.11(0.0)bi	0.13(0.12)bi	0.13(0.12)bi	0.13(0.12)bi	0.12(0.01)	0.15(0.16)	0.23(0.28)	0.23(0.28)
23	7	2	3	0.44(0.07)	0.44(0.07)	0.48(0.1)	0.5(0.18)	0.44(0.07)	0.44(0.07)	0.45(0.07)b	0.45(0.07)b	0.48(0.09)	0.48(0.1)	0.49(0.1)	0.54(0.14)
24	7	2	4	0.39(0.09)	0.39(0.09)	0.44(0.15)	0.42(0.15)	0.4(0.11)	0.4(0.11)	0.4(0.11)b	0.41(0.13)	0.46(0.14)	0.46(0.14)	0.44(0.13)	0.48(0.19)
26	7	10	1	0.11(0.1)	0.09(0.09)	0.18(0.14)	0.2(0.15)	0.04(0.04)b	0.04(0.04)b	0.04(0.04)b	0.05(0.05)b	0.08(0.12)	0.08(0.12)	0.09(0.13)	0.09(0.13)
27	7	10	2	0.09(0.11)	0.1(0.11)	0.16(0.14)	0.24(0.15)	0.02(0.02)b	0.02(0.02)b	0.02(0.02)b	0.04(0.04)b	0.06(0.09)	0.06(0.09)	0.05(0.07)	0.06(0.09)
28	7	10	3	0.36(0.16)	0.36(0.17)	0.42(0.21)	0.43(0.21)	0.18(0.12)b	0.19(0.13)b	0.22(0.17)b	0.24(0.16)b	0.2(0.17)	0.2(0.17)	0.18(0.16)	0.19(0.16)
29	7	10	4	0.22(0.15)	0.23(0.15)	0.28(0.19)	0.33(0.18)	0.13(0.14)b	0.12(0.14)b	0.16(0.16)b	0.17(0.18)b	0.14(0.16)	0.14(0.16)	0.14(0.16)	0.17(0.18)
31	1	4	1	0.49(0.13)	0.49(0.13)	0.52(0.13)	0.58(0.15)	0.46(0.11)i	0.46(0.12)i	0.48(0.12)bi	0.49(0.11)bi	0.59(0.09)	0.59(0.09)	0.59(0.09)	0.59(0.09)
32	1	4	2	0.06(0.1)	0.06(0.09)	0.09(0.13)	0.13(0.14)	0.05(0.08)i	0.05(0.08)i	0.06(0.1)i	0.07(0.1)i	0.12(0.11)	0.12(0.11)	0.12(0.11)	0.12(0.11)
33	1	4	3	0.46(0.13)	0.44(0.11)	0.5(0.13)	0.52(0.16)	0.42(0.1)bi	0.42(0.09)bi	0.44(0.09)bi	0.45(0.09)bi	0.56(0.11)	0.56(0.11)	0.56(0.11)	0.56(0.11)
34	1	4	4	0.04(0.08)	0.04(0.08)	0.06(0.14)	0.08(0.11)	0.03(0.07)i	0.03(0.07)i	0.03(0.05)bi	0.04(0.07)bi	0.1(0.13)	0.1(0.13)	0.1(0.13)	0.1(0.13)
36	2	4	1	0.52(0.17)	0.5(0.17)	0.58(0.17)	0.6(0.18)	0.43(0.14)bi	0.42(0.13)bi	0.46(0.16)bi	0.47(0.15)bi	0.85(0.14)	0.85(0.14)	0.85(0.14)	0.85(0.14)
37	2	4	2	0.05(0.04)	0.06(0.06)	0.09(0.08)	0.15(0.15)	0.04(0.03)bi	0.04(0.03)i	0.05(0.04)bi	0.07(0.06)bi	0.13(0.09)	0.13(0.09)	0.13(0.09)	0.13(0.09)
38	2	4	3	0.55(0.13)	0.56(0.12)	0.61(0.15)	0.67(0.16)	0.5(0.09)i	0.5(0.09)bi	0.53(0.11)bi	0.54(0.12)bi	0.88(0.12)	0.88(0.12)	0.88(0.12)	0.88(0.12)
39	2	4	4	0.04(0.02)	0.04(0.03)	0.1(0.11)	0.09(0.08)	0.03(0.01)bi	0.03(0.01)bi	0.04(0.02)bi	0.04(0.03)bi	0.11(0.09)	0.11(0.09)	0.11(0.09)	0.11(0.09)
41	7	4	1	0.26(0.15)	0.3(0.18)	0.32(0.19)	0.4(0.23)	0.19(0.11)bi	0.18(0.09)bi	0.21(0.11)bi	0.25(0.17)bi	0.38(0.21)	0.38(0.21)	0.38(0.21)	0.39(0.22)
42	7	4	2	0.04(0.02)	0.04(0.02)	0.04(0.03)	0.06(0.07)	0.02(0.01)bi	0.02(0.01)bi	0.03(0.02)bi	0.03(0.02)bi	0.09(0.13)	0.09(0.13)	0.09(0.12)	0.11(0.14)
43	7	4	3	0.43(0.13)	0.44(0.14)	0.5(0.14)	0.58(0.15)	0.42(0.13)i	0.41(0.13)i	0.43(0.13)bi	0.44(0.13)bi	0.52(0.16)	0.52(0.16)	0.54(0.16)	0.54(0.17)
44	7	4	4	0.11(0.05)	0.12(0.07)	0.13(0.06)	0.17(0.11)	0.1(0.05)i	0.09(0.05)bi	0.11(0.05)bi	0.11(0.05)bi	0.18(0.1)	0.18(0.1)	0.19(0.11)	0.22(0.13)
Tchebychef UF															
5	1	2	-	0.14(0.05)	0.15(0.05)	0.2(0.11)	0.24(0.1)	0.13(0.04)	0.13(0.04)b	0.14(0.04)bi	0.15(0.07)bi	0.12(0.01)i	0.12(0.01)i	0.17(0.05)	0.19(0.06)
10	1	10	-	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.04)	0.08(0.05)	0.05(0.02)bi	0.05(0.02)i	0.06(0.03)	0.07(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)	0.06(0.03)
15	2	2	-	0.32(0.01)	0.34(0.04)	0.43(0.11)	0.46(0.15)	0.32(0.0)i	0.32(0.0)bi	0.33(0.05)bi	0.34(0.05)bi	0.33(0.01)	0.33(0.01)	0.36(0.09)	0.47(0.15)
20	2	10	-	0.08(0.01)	0.08(0.01)	0.11(0.04)	0.11(0.04)	0.07(0.01)bi	0.07(0.01)bi	0.08(0.02)bi	0.09(0.02)i	0.11(0.03)	0.11(0.03)	0.11(0.03)	0.11(0.03)
25	7	2	-	0.04(0.01)	0.04(0.02)	0.1(0.15)	0.16(0.19)	0.04(0.0)bi	0.04(0.0)bi	0.04(0.01)bi	0.04(0.01)bi	0.04(0.0)	0.04(0.0)	0.06(0.06)	0.14(0.19)
30	7	10	-	0.12(0.02)	0.13(0.01)	0.14(0.02)	0.15(0.03)	0.1(0.01)b	0.1(0.01)b	0.1(0.01)b	0.11(0.01)b	0.07(0.03)i	0.07(0.03)i	0.08(0.04)i	0.08(0.04)i
35	1	4	-	0.06(0.02)	0.06(0.02)	0.08(0.04)	0.08(0.03)	0.05(0.02)bi	0.05(0.02)bi	0.06(0.02)bi	0.06(0.02)bi	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)	0.07(0.03)
40	2	4	-	0.09(0.04)	0.09(0.04)	0.13(0.06)	0.16(0.07)	0.07(0.02)bi	0.07(0.02)bi	0.08(0.04)bi	0.09(0.06)bi	0.17(0.06)	0.17(0.06)	0.17(0.06)	0.17(0.06)
45	7	4	-	0.12(0.05)	0.12(0.05)	0.13(0.09)	0.21(0.1)	0.08(0.02)bi	0.09(0.03)bi	0.1(0.05)bi	0.11(0.05)bi	0.16(0.1)	0.16(0.1)	0.19(0.11)	0.19(0.11)